

Meditation Can Alter the Structure and Biochemistry of the Brain

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A High-Level Overview of Meditation

Meditation has been practiced for thousands of years in various cultures and spiritual traditions. It is not limited to any specific religious or philosophical belief system. It can also be used in non-religious ways.

Purpose of the Article: This article presents a concise synthesis of credible research from neuroscience, cognitive science, and mental health on the effects of meditation. Drawing on three decades of personal practice and observation of others, I integrate findings from peer-reviewed studies with experiential insights to highlight how meditation influences brain function and well-being. To support further exploration, all cited studies are linked to their original journal sources. The work is offered purely for educational purposes and contains no commercial or affiliate content, serving as a contribution to the broader community of readers and researchers.

Introduction

Based on studies of famous thought leaders and researchers like Richard Davidson (neuroscientist), John Kabat-Zinn (professor of medicine), Sara Lazar (psychologist), and Daniel Goleman (psychologist), meditation practices can be categorized into two main styles: focused attention and open monitoring.

In focused attention meditation, we direct our attention to a specific object or focus point, maintaining sustained concentration. Open monitoring meditation involves non-reactively observing and becoming aware of our thoughts, emotions, and sensations without judgment or attachment.

The goal of mindfulness-based meditation, which falls under the open monitoring style, is to develop an alert and open state of perceiving and monitoring mental experiences in the present moment. This includes awareness of perceptions, sensations, thoughts, and emotions as they arise and pass by.

These different styles of meditation aim to regulate attention and enhance reflective awareness of our cognitive and emotional patterns. By practicing focused attention or open monitoring, we can develop better mindfulness and insights into our mental processes.

There are many meditation techniques in different cultures. But they typically involve finding a quiet and comfortable space, adopting a specific posture, and engaging in specific mental exercises or quietude.

During meditation, some people achieve a state of heightened awareness and inner calm by directing their attention to a specific object, like the breath, a mantra, or a particular sensation. The goal is to let go of distracting

thoughts and achieve deep concentration and stillness.

In general, people incorporate meditation into their daily routines as a means of promoting well-being, reducing stress, improving attention, enhancing self-awareness, and gaining unique perceptions.

Scientific research shows that regular meditation practice can have benefits like reducing anxiety, improving emotional regulation, enhancing cognitive function, and promoting physical and mental relaxation during difficult times.

Meditation is increasingly used as a complementary practice in healthcare environments, like mindfulness-based therapies, to support mental and emotional well-being. It is also helpful to sleep better, as I documented a case study of a friend who solved her sleep issues with meditation.

The Meaning of Cortical Thickness and Cortical Thinning

Cortical thickness means the thickness and depth of the outer layer of the brain (cerebral cortex). The cerebral cortex controls higher cognitive functions, like attention, perception, memory, and language.

The cortex consists of layers of neurons for processing sensory information, controlling movement, and supporting complex cognitive processes. Cortical thickness is an important measure because it is associated with brain development, neuroplasticity, and brain health.

The thickness of the cortex can vary from person to person. Various factors (genetics, age, and environmental experiences) influence it. Thicker cortical regions are typically associated with enhanced cognitive abilities and better mental well-being.

Cortical thinning, just the opposite of thickness, means the gradual reduction in the thickness of the cerebral cortex. It is a natural process that occurs with aging. Factors like neurological conditions, stress, and lifestyle choices can influence it.

Cortical thinning typically occurs in specific brain regions and can affect different cognitive functions depending on the areas involved.

Some degree of cortical thinning is considered a normal part of aging. However, excessive or accelerated thinning might indicate neurological disorders like Alzheimer's or other forms of dementia.

Adverse changes in cortical thickness, indicating thinning, are also observed in patients with psychiatric conditions like schizophrenia or depression.

Understanding cortical thinning and its implications is essential in neurobiology as it provides insights into the structural changes that occur in the aging brain and neurological conditions.

Ongoing research continues to explore the underlying mechanisms of cortical thinning and its relationship to cognitive decline and mental health, to develop strategies to promote brain health and mitigate the risks of age-related cognitive decline.

An Overview of Insights from Literature on How Meditation Positively Affects Cortical Thickness

This outstanding study, published in *Neuroreport* in 2006 as a pioneer in meditation research in neuroscience, informed previous research that indicated that long-term meditation practice was associated with altered resting electroencephalogram patterns, suggesting long-lasting changes in brain activity.

Researchers hypothesized that “meditation practice might be associated with changes in the brain’s physical structure. Magnetic resonance imaging assessed cortical thickness in 20 participants with extensive Insight meditation experience, which involved focused attention to internal experiences.”

They found that “brain regions associated with attention, interoception, and sensory processing were thicker in meditation participants than in matched controls, including the prefrontal cortex and right anterior insula.”

“Between-group differences in prefrontal cortical thickness were most pronounced in older participants, suggesting that meditation might offset age-related cortical thinning. The thickness of the two regions correlated with the meditation experience. These data provided the first structural evidence for experience-dependent cortical plasticity associated with meditation practice.”

Recent studies indicate that meditation can impact cortical thickness in regions involved in attention, self-awareness, interoception, and sensory processing.

However, the specific mechanisms underlying the effects of meditation on cortical thickness are still being investigated. Therefore, more research is needed to understand the relationship entirely.

As documented in **this 2023 study**, “a distinct pattern of cortical thinning and resultant changes in cognition and function characterizes Alzheimer’s. These result in prominent deficits in cognitive-motor automaticity.”

The key points and concepts in the literature are neuroplasticity, neurogenesis, stress reduction, self-regulation, enhanced attention, improved memory, emotional regulation, and lowered mind-wandering.

I want to touch on these critical points briefly with summaries of studies.

This magnetoencephalography study in 2018 informed that “mindfulness meditation is related to long-lasting changes in hippocampal functional topology during a resting state.”

These types of studies indicate that meditation can induce neuroplasticity (the brain’s ability to change and reorganize itself). They indicate that regular meditation practice might lead to structural changes in the brain, increasing its cortical thickness.

Studies suggest that meditation might stimulate neurogenesis, the birth of new neurons, particularly in the hippocampus, **increasing gray matter density**. Increased neurogenesis in the hippocampus might contribute to changes in cortical thickness.

Based on studies conducted until 2015, researchers found that meditation can trigger neurotransmitters that modulate psychological disorders like anxiety. **This 2015 study** reviewed the psychological effects of meditation, the role of neurotransmitters, and studies using EEG and fMRI.

Greater cortical thickness **in the prefrontal cortex** has been associated with better attentional control and the ability to sustain focus.

The thicker cortex facilitates stronger neural connections, enhancing the coordination and communication between brain areas (the prefrontal and parietal cortices) involved in attention.

Greater cortical thickness in the hippocampus is linked to better memory performance, particularly in tasks involving the acquisition and retrieval of new information. It indicates a more significant number of neurons, synapses, and dendritic connections, which support the formation and storage of memories. **Thinning of the hippocampus** indicates disorders.

Cortical thickness is influenced by synaptic density, which refers to the number and strength of connections between neurons. Greater synaptic density in specific cortical regions can enhance the neural networks involved in attention and memory processes.

Myelin (a fatty substance that wraps nerve fibers) is crucial in neural transmission. Thicker cortical regions have higher myelination, enabling faster communication between neurons. **According to a hypothesis**, "frontal theta induced by meditation produces a molecular cascade that increases myelin and improves connectivity."

Cortical thickness can affect the distribution and availability of neurotransmitters. The density and balance of **therapeutic neurotransmitter** Dr Mehmet Yildiz | digital mehmet.com | © 2025 influence cognitive processes.

Meditation techniques involve relaxation and stress reduction. Oxidative stress can adversely affect the brain, including the shrinkage of brain regions. By reducing stress levels, meditation might promote the preservation or growth of cortical thickness.

This 2009 study in the Journal of Neurosciences conducted three months of intensive meditation training. "Meditation reduced variability in attentional processing of target tones, indicating enhanced theta-band phase consistency of oscillatory neural responses over anterior brain areas and reduced reaction time variability."

Mind-wandering, a state of spontaneous and uncontrolled thoughts, is associated with cortical thinning. Meditation can lower mind-wandering. By enhancing attentional control and reducing mind-wandering, meditation might contribute to preserving cortical thickness.

This 2020 review study provided a theoretical framework highlighting the neurocognitive mechanisms by which contemplative practices influence the neural and phenomenological processes underlying random thoughts, which include mind-wandering, dreaming, and creative thinking.

"Mind-wandering in the context of meditation provides individuals a unique and intimate opportunity to closely examine the nature of the wandering mind, cultivating an awareness of ongoing thought patterns while simultaneously cultivating equanimity and compassion towards the content of thoughts, interpretations, and bodily sensations."

Clinical trials show mindfulness meditation can improve emotion processing. Some studies link emotional regulation to cortical thickness.

For example, **this 2022 study** stated that "Momentary emotion regulation strategy use mediated the association between cortical thickness in right lateral prefrontal cortex assessed before the pandemic and mental health during the pandemic."

Conclusions and Key Takeaways

Studies indicate that **meditation can increase cortical thickness** in brain regions associated with attention, interception, and sensory processing.

These changes are most pronounced in older people, suggesting meditation may offset age-related cortical thinning.

The thickening of these brain regions is associated with improved attentional control and memory performance.

Meditation can promote neuroplasticity, the brain's ability to change and reorganize, and stimulate neurogenesis, the creation of new neurons.

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These processes occur primarily in the hippocampus, a structure essential for memory formation, learning, and emotional regulation. The thicker cortex resulting from meditation practice facilitates stronger neural connections and enhances coordination between brain areas involved in attention and memory.

Furthermore, meditation can reduce stress levels and mind-wandering while promoting emotional regulation. By reducing stress and enhancing attentional control, meditation might help preserve cortical thickness and support cognitive functions.

Empirical findings so far provide compelling evidence for the benefits of meditation in maintaining brain health and cognitive function.

Takeaways

- 1 — *Meditation is a tool that everyone can use differently. There is no right or wrong way. It depends on your choice. However, some people cannot meditate for various reasons, so please don't force yourself.*
- 2 — *Unlike common beliefs, meditation can initially stress the brain significantly. Therefore, begin with small sessions, like five to ten minutes, and gradually increase the duration as your brain becomes more tolerant, and you feel more comfortable.*
- 3 — *Consistency is critical to rewiring the brain. Therefore make meditation a regular practice by integrating it into your daily routine. Find a schedule that works for you and stick to it to create a habit.*
- 4 — *The most accessible anchor is using your breath for your attention. Observe your thoughts as they arise and gently let them go, returning your focus to the breath.*
- 5 — *Practice observing and labeling your thoughts and feelings without judging them. Develop a nonreactive attitude towards them, allowing them to come and go naturally.*
- 6 — *Experiment with various types of meditation to discover what resonates with you and addresses your specific needs. Some people enjoy chanting and using mantras. Some people incorporate visualization or sounds.*
- 7 — *Maintain a positive mindset. Develop optimism and an open mindset to embrace the practice. You need to believe in the benefits of meditation for your well-being.*
- 8 — *Express appreciation to your body and mind for providing you with the opportunity to engage in meditation. Acknowledge the gift of self-care and the nourishment it brings. Always practice self-compassion and self-love in your journey.*

While meditation can benefit many, some people may face challenges due to underlying health conditions or differences in neural wiring. It's crucial to listen to your body and mind and not force yourself into a practice that might not suit you.

If you find that traditional forms of meditation do not resonate with you and cause distress, it's okay to explore alternative practices or obtain guidance from qualified professionals. The key is to honor your boundaries and prioritize your well-being.

The goal of meditation is subjective. It is not to achieve a specific outcome or conform to a rigid set of rules. Instead, it's about finding a practice that brings peace, clarity, and self-awareness. Embrace the diversity of meditative approaches and choose what works best for you.

I personally meditate three times daily. I also enjoy doing daily activities such as mindfulness practices and leveraging the meditative power of [neurobics](#), which can also rewire the brain and prevent cognitive decline. You may also check out [a relevant and more comprehensive story](#) published on Medium.com.

Thank you for reading my perspectives. I wish you a healthy and peaceful life.

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